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Research Article

**CLINICAL SPECTRUM OF FISTULA IN ANO AT TERTIARY
CARE HOSPITAL**

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the clinical spectrum of fistula in ano at tertiary care hospital.

Patients and Methods: The six months clinical study was conducted at tertiary care hospital on fifty participants. The specific patients of fistula in ano were clinically diagnosed and selected randomly. The clinical history was obtained in all the patients and the clinical examination including general physical examination, per rectal and proctoscopic was done in all individuals. All the patients were explored by routine investigations as ECG, chest, X-Ray before surgery. Fistulogram was done in selected cases and the patients were managed with fistulectomy or fistulotomy for fistulae and were had follow up visits for six months while the frequency / percentages (%) and means $\pm$ SD computed for study variables.

Results: during one year study period total fifty patients of fistula in ano were explored and studied. the frequency for male and female population was 40 (80%) and 10 (20%) with mean $\pm$ sd for age of male and female individuals was 48.84 ± 7.83 and 43.94 ± 6.95 respectively. regarding the mode of presentation discharge 11 (22%), pain and swelling 04 (8.0%), peri anal irritation 05 (10%), past history of peri anal abscess 30 (60%), number of external opening one (94%) and ≥ 2 (6.0%), the types of surgical treatment fistulectomy 45 (90%), fistulotomy 04 (8.0%), fistulectomy with lateral sphincterotomy 01 (2.0) and the post operative outcomes complete healing 40 (80%), bleeding 03 (6.0%), recurrence of fistula 05 (10%) and haematoma 02 (4.0%).

Conclusion: Fistula in ano is an important, commonest ailment and all the cases should bear surgery, fistulectomy is better than fistulotomy

Keywords: Fistulectomy, Fistula in ano and fistulotomy

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INTRODUCTION:

Fistula-in-ano types good majority treatable benign lesions of the rectum and anal canal. 90% or so of these instances are stop effects of crypto-glandular infections. It is not an existence threatening illnesses however reasons lot of problems inconveniences to lead a normal life. It is a chronic sickness and can only be met with surgery [1]. Otherwise it is forming abscesses causing troublesome pain [2]. It might also burst to discharge serous or purulent discharge which will come in the way of events existence and social mixing of suffer with others [3]. Though it is common disorder in human beings, the conservative administration is no longer a permanent alleviation in these cases. The records given by using the affected person and cautious normal bodily examination with an exact source of light, a proctoscope and a meticulous digital rectal examination [4]. In some instances fistulogram and chest x-ray are wished to diagnose the circumstance with associated conditions and etiological factors. The majority of these infections are acute and substantial minority is contributed by chronic, low grade infections, hence ache being to various etiologies [5] The common pathogenesis however is the bursting open of an acute or inadequately treated ano-rectal abscess into the peri-anal skin. Despite the easy diagnosis, organising a treatment is complicated on two accounts; firstly, many sufferers have a tendency to let their sickness nag them as a substitute than being concern to examination, frequently proudly owning to site of the disease [6]. The most essential 2nd factor is that a sizeable percent of these diseases persist or recur when the right modality of surgical treatment is now not adopted or when submit operative care is inadequate [7]. So these conditions have an effect on the young and middle aged humans inflicting loss of treasured productive man hours.

Since the day of disease, it used to be handled by using surgery. With the recent clear awareness of the members of the family of the fistula with anal sphincters, the surgical treatment has turn out to be extra easier [8]. Usually the fistula-in-ano excised and saved open to heal via granulation tissue. This system takes long duration to heal completely. In this work one of the most common disorder is selected to learn about its evidence and management and comply with up of the patient.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The six months clinical study was conducted at tertiary care hospital on fifty participants. The specific patients of fistula in ano were clinically diagnosed and selected randomly. The clinical history was obtained in all the patients and the clinical examination including general physical examination, per rectal and proctoscopic was done in all individuals. All the patients were explored by routine investigations as ECG, chest, X-Ray before surgery. Fistulogram was done in selected cases and the patients were managed with fistulectomy or fistulotomy for fistulae and were had follow up visits for six months. The data was recruited on pre-designed proforma while analyzed in SPSS to manipulate the frequencies, percentages and mean $\pm$ SD.

RESULTS:

During one year study period total fifty patients of fistula in ano were explored and studied. The frequency for male and female population was 40 (80%) and 10 (20%) with mean $\pm$ SD for age of male and female individuals was 48.84 ± 7.83 and 43.94 ± 6.95 respectively. The demographical and clinical profile of study population is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

Parameter	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage (%)
AGE (yrs)		
20-29	06	12
30-39	05	10
40-49	31	62
50+	08	16
GENDER		
Male	40	80
Female	10	20
MODE OF PRESENTATION		
Discharge	11	22
Pain and swelling	04	8.0
Peri anal irritation	05	10
Past history of peri anal abscess	30	60
NUMBER OF EXTERNAL OPENING		
1	47	94
≥2	03	6.0
TYPES OF SURGICAL TREATMENT		
Fistulectomy	45	90
Fistulotomy	04	8.0
Fistulectomy with lateral Sphincterotomy	01	2.0
POST OPERATIVE OUTCOMES		
Complete healing	40	80
Bleeding	03	6.0
Recurrence of fistula	05	10
Haematoma	02	4.0

DISCUSSION:

In current series of 50 cases, majority of patients (62%) were in 40-49 year age and is consistent with the former study [9]. Regarding gender distribution majority of the patients (80%) was male population and is similar with the former study [10]. The findings reading the mode of presentation are consistent with the former study while the observations for number of external openings are also consistent with the former study [11]. The best careful solution for should annihilate sepsis and

advance recuperating of the tract, in the meantime as keeping the sphincters and the component of self control [12]. For the straightforward and most distal fistulae, conventional careful treatment, for example, expose of the fistula tract as a whole transection of the tissue between the fistula tract and anoderm is extremely gigantic with an accomplishment of up to 100%. Albeit articulated incontinence charges following fistula surgery is truly factor and is affected by method for some components, incontinence rate subsequent to exposing of

intersphincteric and distal fistulae is by all accounts underneath 10% [13]. To enhance the restoration rates, affected person resolution is imperative, and manage of sepsis, identification of secondary extensions and tracts of the fistula from the anal canal earlier than any attempt of repair is strongly suggested [14].

CONCLUSION:

Fistula in ano is an important, commonest ailment due to cryptoglandular infection (anal glands) and as a complication of ano rectal abscess and in this learn about all the cases should bear surgery, fistulectomy is better than fistulotomy.

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